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Research Article

**UTILIZATION OF OVER THE COUNTER MEDICATION &
ANTIBIOTICS AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS AMONG
PREGNANT FEMALES**Dr Azka Khan, Dr Ghazala Muzaffar, Dr Rabbia Rasheed
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Abstract:

Objective: The usage of the OTCMs (Over the Counter Medications) is very common practice in whole world. The use of OTCMs among females with pregnancy is a matter of special concern and these pose danger for the maternal as well as fetal health. The main purpose of this research work was to evaluate the utilization of the OTCMs by the females with pregnancy and factors having association with this matter. **Methodology:** This is a transverse research and we administered an organized questionnaire at Obstetric Department of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. We conducted a survey of total three hundred and fifty four pregnant females in this research work.

Result: Total 32.0% participants of this research work utilized OTCMs without any prescription at least one time in the duration of last gestation period. Paracetamol was the very common utilized OTCM (22.0%). The main source of awareness for the patients were pharmacists (53.0%). Correct awareness about drugs was present with association with the utilization of OTCMs drug.

Conclusion: The usage of the OTCMs and other antibiotics in period of gestation is much frequent practice in pregnant females of our country. There is need increase the general knowledge about the usage of OTCMs in the period of pregnancy without any prescription. Media and pharmacists can provide the precise knowledge regarding this topic which can be beneficial.

KEY WORD: Pregnancy, OTCMs, prescription, paracetamol, methodology, Ganga Ram.

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INTRODUCTION:

According to WHO, OTCM is the choice and utilization of the medicines by persons for the treatment of self-recognized symptoms or illnesses [1]. The utilization of the non-prescribed of OTCMs is much frequent in the whole world [2, 3]. One research work reported that about 89.0% pregnant females in USA were using OTCMs at least one time in their gestation period [3]. There are also reports of high prevalence from the countries of Europe as 95.0% in the Netherlands, 93.0% in Iceland and 92.0% in Finland, there is also very high occurrence of this utilization in Pakistan and Nigeria [4-6]. Most common utilized drugs by the females with pregnancy are antibiotics, anti-allergy, paracetamol and antacids. There is debate that the utilization of such medicines decreases the burden of the visit in the hospitals as well as costs of the health care facilities. Various research works raised concerns over utilization of the OTCMs in the duration of pregnancy [7, 8].

There is very little information available in our country about the use of OTCMs by females having pregnancy. One research work conducted in Karachi in the year of 2013 stated that the use of medicines during pregnancy duration was 40.0% [9]. That research work only saw the prescribed medication, so the findings of that research work are able to generalize on all population of our country. In this research work, we also wanted to access the associated factors that have relation with the usage of drugs without any prescription among pregnant females of our country.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a transverse research work depending upon a well-organized questionnaire performed at Obstetric

Department of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. We approached all the females visiting the Obstetric Department of this institute. We requested all the females in waiting room to participate in this research work. We included only the females pregnant at that time and they were the residents of Lahore. We selected three hundred and fifty-four pregnant females for this research work.

We collected the information on a well-organized Performa. There were 4 sections in Performa as sociodemographic, attitude, knowledge & practice section. In the section of knowledge, we asked about their knowledge regarding risks of particular medicines. The statement for the pregnant female to answer was present in attitude section. The section of practice contained the medicines which were being used by patients. We also asked the females with pregnancy to report about the use of OTCMs. We carried out piloting on 10.0% of total population, to check the ambiguities. SPSS V. 23 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. We also run the crude odds ratio & multivariate model. The ethical committee of the institute gave the permission to conduct this research work. We took the written consent from every female after explaining them the purpose of this research work. We did not collect any personal information from females as name or address.

RESULTS:

We recruited total 354 females with pregnancy in this research work. A sum of total 322 (91.0%) pregnant females completed this research work and thirty two females left the survey. The socio-demographic traits of the females are present in Table-1.

Table-I: Personal and Demographic Characteristics on OCTMs usage during pregnancy.

Variables		No	Percentage
Age	<20	8.0	2.5
	20-30	217.0	67.0
	31-41	82.0	25.5
	>40	15.0	5.0
Education	Elementary	9.0	3.0
	Intermediate	15.0	5.0
	High school	114.0	35.0
	Bachelor	162.0	50.0
	Higher education	22.0	7.0
Occupation	House-wife	171.0	53.0
	Student	45.0	14.0
	Health-related employee	14.0	4.0
	Teacher	52.0	16.0

	Others	40.0	13.0
Monthly Income	<3,000	15.0	5.0
	3,000-4,999	66.0	20.0
	5,000-9,999	152.0	47.0
	10,000-20,000	77.0	24.0
	>20,000	12.0	4.0
Pregnancies	1	137.0	43.0
	2	59.0	18.0
	3	49.0	15.0
	4	26.0	8.0
	>4	51.0	16.0
Diseases	No disease	200.0	62.0
	Diabetes	28.0	9.0
	Hypertension	8.0	2.5
	Asthma	25.0	8.0
	Hypothyroidism	25.0	9.0
	Anemia	42.0	13.0
	Others	32.0	10.0

About 32.0% females had utilized the medicines at least one time in their pregnancy. Paracetamol & antibiotics were the most frequently obtained OTCMs with the prescription. Whereas without prescription, the most common used drugs were paracetamol as well as herbal medicines.

Fifty percent females of this research work were aware about the fact that in the months of pregnancy the utilization of the medicines should be according to prescription. Ninety percent females were present with the opinion that if they will feel uneasy in pregnancy they will directly go to the pharmacists and get their concern medicine without any prescription. This was despite 85.0% were present with the view that OCT medicines are also dangerous for the fetus.

The main source of information for the OTCMs were pharmacists in 53.0%, medication pamphlets in 28.0%, media in 27.0%, and family member in 11.0% and friends in 4.0%. We took the response as multiple response. We performed the bivariate analysis to determine the factors linked with the utilization of the use of OTCM in period of pregnancy. The results are present in Table-2.

We found no relationship between the usage of OTCM and socio-demographic variables. Females who were aware about herbal medications use as well as aspirin without any prescription, were more likely not to utilize OTCM without permission. (OR 1.650, CI 1.00-2.70, OR 1.780, CI 1.00-3.10). But, pregnant females who were not aware about antacid safety and utilization in the duration of pregnancy, were more likely to utilize OTCMs without any prescription (OR 1.90, CI 1.10-3.0).

Table-II: Table showing the factors associated with OTC drug usage.

Factors		OTCMs use during pregnancy				RR	95% CI
		Yes ; n=103		No ; n=219			
		No	Percent	No	Percent		
Age	Age <= 30	71.0	69.0	154.0	70.0	1.060	0.640 - 1.770
	Age > 30	32.0	31.0	65.0	30.0		
Education	lower education	49.0	48.0	89.0	41.0	1.320	0.820 - 2.120
	higher education	54.0	52.0	130.0	59.0		
Occupation	House wife	54.0	52.0	117.0	53.0	1.040	0.650 - 1.660
	Employee women	49.0	38.0	102.0	47.0		
Income	Low income family	31.0	30.0	50.0	23.0	1.450	0.860 - 2.460
	High income family	72.0	70.0	169.0	77.0		
Pregnancy	First pregnancy	41.0	40.0	96.0	44.0	1.180	0.730 - 1.900
	Multiple pregnancy	62.0	60.0	123.0	52.5		
Drugs Awareness	Not knowledgeable	46.0	45.0	86.0	39.0	1.240	0.770 - 2.000
	Knowledgeable	57.0	55.0	133.0	61.0		

DISCUSSION:

This research work was the first research work in our country about OTCMs usage among pregnant females. We compared the findings with the high proportion of the pregnant females utilizing OTCMs in USA and other countries of Europe [3, 4], approximately 32.0% females in this research work stated the use of OTCMs at least one time in the duration of their gestation period. Most of our study population was aware about the adverse impacts of such utilization on maternal as well fetal health. There were also fear that some of our females did not tell us about their use of OTCMs. Amazingly, there was no association of socio-demographic traits, economic status, education, age of the patient and awareness about medicines with the OTCMs usage. This finding is not similar with the results of the research work conducted in Nigeria [10], which displayed that use of OTCM in the period of pregnancy was much common in unemployed women and multigravida. Lupattelli in his research work stated that elder females, uneducated females, housewives and females with no planned pregnancy were more involved in the use of such drugs [2]. We did not discover in this research work that females with less awareness about the damages of such drugs were more likely to use the OTCMs in their gestation period. This finding is also similar with other research works conducted in this field [5, 6]. Some international research works stated herbal medication, paracetamol and vitamins to be the main OTCMs used by the pregnant females [4-6]. Bin Abdulhak confirmed his research work that about 78.0% pharmacies were giving the antibiotics without prescription [11] in Saudi Arabia. The high utilization of the antibiotics in females with pregnancy is very threatening state. This issue needs a large scale investigation and formulation of proper health measures. Pharmacists were the main source of proving these medicines to the pregnant females, Abeje also gave the similar results that females who were living away from the health care facilities, were approaching pharmacies to obtain the medication directly without any prescription. This research work carried out on the pregnant females of only one city, so we cannot generalize the findings of this research work on whole country. There is need of further research works to consolidate the findings of this research work and to know the reasons behind the use of OTCMs.

CONCLUSION:

This research work showed that use of OTCMs is much frequent among pregnant females of our community. Most of the females with pregnancy are using the drugs with no pregnancy and the most important source are the medical pamphlets, media and pharmacists. There is also use of the antibiotics with no prescription of the doctors. This finding conclude that most of the population is not aware about the potential dangers having association with the use of antibiotics in the pregnant females for maternal & fetal health.

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